

Translational Loss of Contextual Puns in Patras Bukhari's Selected Short Stories

Amna Saeed, Fatima Nagrah

Article Info

Article History

Received:
August 16, 2020

Accepted:
November 05, 2020

Keywords

Translation Studies,
Translational Loss,
Humor, Stylistics,
Stylistic devices,
Semantic Meaning

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5745933

Abstract

This qualitative research aims to stylistically analyze and investigate the translational loss of humor in Patras Bukhari's selected short stories. Patras Bukhari is known for his great command on Urdu language and his vast understanding of it. Even though his contribution in literature is less in volume, whatever he has written gives him a prominent place in Urdu Literature. He is most popular for repartee and humor, which is exquisite, with hints of spirited liveliness and good taste. He draws humor with situations more than words and makes groups and classes his target instead of individuals. His humorous writings are a mix of stylistic devices like pun, irony, satire, exaggeration, mockery and insult, which are distinctive in their nature but hard to identify because Patras blends them so eloquently hinting his unique style of expression. Translation of such a blend of stylistic devices in English language, requires complete understanding and awareness of both Urdu and English language cultures. Humor translation is an important part of the literary translation which is highly dependent on certain linguistic features and context. In case of unique humorous work such as Patras's, its English rendering loses the essence of humor. The humor built on word-play and context in the original, is not completely retained in the translations hence, the translational loss of humor takes place. The present study is conducted to stylistically analyze this translational loss of humor and for this purpose, the current study undertakes the perspective of Descriptive Translation Studies. Furthermore, the study derives its research model from Paul Simpson's (2004) theory of 'Stylistics and Humor'. The selected texts have been studied considering the research questions that focus on the deviation in stylistic devices and the semantic difference that occurs due to the difference of source language and target language cultures evident by inadequate word-choices by the translators. All these factors collectively become the underlying reasons for the translational loss of humor.

1. Introduction

Humor is the heart of literature, which brings joy and eases pain, it is a way of understanding the culture and language of a society (Zbaracki, 2003). The way humor is expressed also tells a lot about the speaker/writer's background and mind-set. It is that one part of literature that attracts all kinds of people and of all ages (Zbaracki, 2003). Literary humor brings more opportunities for teachers and parents to bring children to books and to teach them about their own or any culture and language. Due to this, humor has always been thought of as an important source of cultural exchange and hence attempts of translating it have been made around the world (Zbaracki, 2003).

Humor translation has an important status in the literary translation. The linguistic and cultural features of humor bring about some major problems for the translators. These problems can be due to the unequal structures of the source and target languages (Hosseini., et al, 2017). Translation however, provides the translators the opportunities of being creative to produce a version that has the same humorous effect as the original (Hosseini., et al, 2017). Humor is not an easy concept to write about and poses many challenges for translators. It is not a new or a modern phenomenon, but more attention is being paid to it in the modern times (Venuti, 2000). The concept of humor is highly depended not only on the cultural background of the interpreters and translators, but also the different languages that the humor is expressed in. The term 'humor' originated from a Latin word 'umor' which means fluids and was only used in the field of medicine, later it reached our times but with a wider meaning and associations. Today, it is used as an umbrella term that covers different concepts like 'fun', 'comedy', 'ridiculous' and more (Chiaro, 2010).

The concept of humor has been studied from different perspectives of philosophy and psychology and linguistics is no exception. It has been studied from different aspects and have collectively been considered a

complex genre for translation. It is believed that humor can transfer from one language to another, but not without difficulty. Humor in any text is built through certain word-choices of the writer and each of which carry a certain meaning that helps the reader understand the context and eventually get to the humorous aspect of the text. Lei (2010) explained that humor is shared by people from all regions and nations. However, due to the difference of cultures and languages it is impossible for all the people to share the same sense of humor. Humor therefore, is language and culture specific. When attempts of translating humor are made, the translators are required to focus on the culture-specific word-choices to retain them in their translations. If the translators succeed in carrying the meaning and intention of the author in the translations, we can call their choices 'adequate', this is the lexical transformation. When it comes to the translation of humorous texts, Chiaro (2010) compares the complicity of the translation of poetry and songs with humor and concludes that 'humor easily wins the first prize'.

There are many problems regarding the process of humor translation, even though it is understood that not everything is in the hands of the translators. A Lithuanian linguist Pazusis cites Eco, who says that "by admitting that a certain piece of text is untranslatable, the translator accepts his own defeat" (Baranauskiene, 2012, p.2). With this it should also be noted that the structure of both the source language (SL) and the target language (TL) have to be taken in consideration by the translators. While dealing with humorous texts the translators need to be clear about what they require to focus on primarily. If the focus is on retaining the meaning of the original in the target text then the lexical choices and style of the author is to be carefully understood. So that even where finding the exact words with similar connotations becomes impossible, the translator can transfer the essence of the original in the target text to avoid the translational loss of humor (Baranauskiene, 2012).

Humor is understood to be formed and shaped by culture, the experiences that human beings share as members of a certain culture are the basis for the jokes, puns, humorous observations, satires, ironies and punchlines that strike us as funny or amusing. It is in the language that the humor is embedded, we can understand a language and its culture through humor. It exists across all languages and cultures as an essential human characteristic, the need for lightheartedness and amusement makes humor a central aspect of human interaction (Cisneros, et al., 2006).

Sayyad Ahmad Shah (Patras Bukhari) is a prominent literary figure in Urdu literature and an outstanding giant in the genre of humor. He gained widespread acclaim after publishing his book "*Patras ke Mazameen*" (Patras's Essays), which is an asset in Urdu humor writing. *Patras k Mazameen* is the brainchild of Patras's creative mind. He has also written and expressed his views on different fields of life other than humor. But it was his humorous work that got the most attention in the literary world. Patras always took literature very seriously and explored it in detail and depth. His work despite being written in first half of the twentieth century, is an all-time living piece of literature (Rumi, 2006).

Patras Bukhari's humor comprises of the aforementioned ideas regarding humor. The current study analyzes the humorous short stories by Patras Bukhari and their English translations to understand how humor and meaning are distorted in the TT. It aims to address the loss of meaning and essence of the original in the TT. The selected texts are rich in humor and cultural connotations and display creativity of the author and his command on language. Moreover, since Patras has a prominent standing in the literary world any attempts of translating his work need to be carefully handled.

Statement of the Problem/Thesis Statement

Different languages have different linguistic structures with distinct stylistic and semantic contents, prominent on different levels of the language system. The stylistic content and meaning are primarily based on the incongruities formed by the word-choices, which create humor in the texts. When attempts of translating humorous texts from one language into another are made, the translational loss takes place. This translational loss is based on the word-choices of the translator, which play a vital role in conveying humor in the ST to the target audience. The current study examines the loss of humor due to stylistic deviation and semantic difference in the translations of Patras Bukhari's selected short stories based on the word-choices of the author in the ST and the translators in the TT.

Note on Translators

The translator of the selected short stories, Matt Reeck is an American writer and translator. He has published many translations in India and the United States. He is a Fulbright scholar and has worked on the works of Urdu literature. His areas of interest are modern prose traditions, ethnography, description and translation. The languages he has worked on or has knowledge of are, French, Hindi, Korean and Urdu. Along with his co-translator, Aftab Ahmed, he has translated the works of Saadat Hassan Manto, Patras Bukhari, Premchand and hindi poetry as well. Aftab Ahmad is an Indian translator, he was the director of the American Institute of Urdu Studies Program in Lucknow. He completed his doctorate in Urdu Literature from Jawaharlal Nehru University. In 2006, he joined UC-Berkeley as a lecture and now teaches at Columbia University. The selected translations for the current study were published in '*Annual of Urdu Studies*', Volume 23, 2008, a

journal annually published at the University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA. The journal provides scholars working on Urdu humanities a forum to publish articles, translations and views.

Methodology

This study is conducted under the perspective of Descriptive Translation Studies, also known as Translation Theory. In comparison to the other disciplines, Translation Studies is a relatively new area of research. It began from the second half of the twentieth century and emerged out of other fields such as modern languages, comparative literature, and linguistics (Munday, 2009).

This study is qualitative in nature. Theory of *Stylistics and Humor* put forward by Simpson (2004) to derive the research model of analysis. The theory of *Stylistics and Humor* sheds light on the humor mechanism that is operational at any level of language and the stylistics analysis of humor is the identification of it at any level through the incongruities in language. It also explains that the humor is identified in language through incongruities; any mismatch or a stylistic twist in the patterns of language. The first step is to identify this incongruity, which is apparent through the word-play and then the stylistic devices which are formed because of the word-play. There are some words that work in a text to build humor and the entire text takes a form based on them. In this case, it is safe to say that humor is built based on the word-play in the texts, through this word-play the stylistic devices are built and hence humor becomes operational. In the stylistic analysis, the first step is to identify the *puns* at work to build humor.

To analyze puns and their translational loss, two short stories by Patras Bukhari are selected. Bukhari takes substance for his humor from the living beings, which is why his work is still valid and relatable even today (Gul & Javed, 2012). The selected stories are chosen for analysis because they are among the finest pieces of literary humor. The selected stories had the most humorous content built and developed on contextual puns. Which would further help in the explanation of the contextual puns in the source text and the distortion of the same in the target text

Issues in Translation of Humor in Literature

Humor is described as the art of making subjects appear ridiculous by eliciting attitude of amusement, contempt, scorn or indignation. (Abrams, 1999) It is the criticism on socio-cultural norms, values, notions, and customs of individuals, institutions and social groups to persuade the audiences to adopt the idea it promotes with the help of satirical devices. Pun is a linguistic concept; it is the use of one or several words in different meanings at the same time to produce humor. It functions both on the word level and the phrase level. (Broeder, 2007).

Every language has its own delicacies of vocabulary when creating laughter and humor and it is enjoyed by the natives. Humor is a type of language and linguistics which is created because of mismatch of words, ideas and no proper order. Humor and Language are not separate entities; it is in the language that the humor is embedded. Humor is much like language in its purpose of paving way out for human thoughts. The human thoughts when externalized, carry multiple meanings, emotions and intellect with them. Due to the variety of these thoughts and emotions different opinions and worldviews find their way into the world hence forming different cultures. (Raskin, 1985)

Along with the experiences, humor is constructed based on grammatical structures and semantic content of a language by keeping in mind the aesthetical values and lexis. Due to the difference of what we think and what we say humor requires a deeper analysis on the level of semantics. All the while not ignoring the fact that humor is transmitted through a use of a language structure, all the puns, satires, and incongruities have a linguistic explanation. (Cisneros, et al, 2006). Newmark defines culture as the way of life that forms and shapes the language and practices of the community that follows it (Newmark, 1988). The translator's job is to analyze whether the figurative language used in the original was able to translate the exact same associations and figures in the target text or not (Rasouli & Rahimi, 2014).

Humoristic pieces in literature have a significant role to play in understanding the history and culture of a society. They shed light on the values, morals, norms and traditions, language in use, etc. that are the reflection of the society and their practices. Humor as mentioned above, is of two types; linguistic and cultural. The former focuses on the wordplays such as pun and malapropism, such humor brings forward the non-sense or unfamiliar talk and can be slightly alarming. (Vandaele, 2002). All these literary devices overlap and there can be confusion in understanding the intention of the author, there the role of context becomes relevant.

Humor translation has an important status in the literary translation. The linguistic and cultural features of humor bring about some major problems for the translators. These problems can be due to the unequal structures of the source and target languages. Translation however, provides the translators the opportunities of being creative to produce a version that has the same humorous effect as the original. (Hosseini, et al, 2017). Humor is not an easy concept to write about and poses many challenges for translators. It is not a new or a modern phenomenon, but more attention is being paid to it in the modern times. (Venuti, 2000) The concept of humor is highly depended not only on the cultural background of the interpreters and translators, but also the different languages that the humor is expressed in. The term 'humor' originated from a Latin word 'umor' which means fluids and was only used in the field of medicine, later it reached our times but with a wider meaning and

associations. Today, it is used as an umbrella term that covers different concepts like ‘fun’, ‘comedy’, ‘ridiculous’ and more. (Chiaro, 2010)

Translators need to understand the difference and working of literary texts and standard language use. Literary texts are studied from the perspective of language, culture and society and literary scholars have invested in their understanding by considering different aspects. Translation can be studied from many different perspectives; philosophical, physiological, linguistics, literature, stylistics, criticism etc. In literature, no other mode has been studied in such detail as poetry and its translation. Translators study poetry from all its aspects including the phonemic and literal translations, metrical and rhymed translations, poetry into prose, blank-verse translation and finally interpretation. In the attempt to translate poetry, whatever appears to be simple is not so and translators have to be very careful to retain the meaning in the translation. Compared to the debate on poetry translation, not much time is spent on prose translation. One explanation could be the higher status poetry holds in the literary world and due to the popular notion, that novel follows a simpler structure and is easy to translate. But although this notion exists, prose needs to be dealt with carefully by keeping in mind the inseparability of form and content. Even in prose, the text gives and follows a certain tone, which is a special quality of a text and that gets lost in translation. (Bassnett, 2002)

The languages differ in what they convey and not in what they might, the contents of what they convey refers to their grammatical and lexical forms and that can be observed at any level of the language system e.g. semantics etc. (Venuti, 2000). In prose, the linguistic differences are to be carefully considered e.g. pun is an extremely language dependent word-play and serves a specific function; to express humor and satire hence, it needs to be more carefully handled when attempts of translating it are made. When the attempts of translating from one language into another are made, linguistic features do not remain the only concern of the translators. In the words of Bassnett (2002, p.13) “language, then, is the heart within the body of the culture and it is the interaction between the two that results in the continuation of life-energy.” pointing that the language and culture are interlinked, and it is through the understanding of these that the meaning is created and understood. Culture is described as the norms, traditions, social habits and values of a society. (Guo, 2012). Vermeer (1992) refers to culture as the norms, conventions and opinions which determine the behavior of a society and all results of this behavior. Language is included and effected by the results, and it is this relationship between language and culture that forms the basis of the Descriptive Translation Studies.

Pun as a Stylistic Device:

Pun, as a literary and stylistic device, is a type of word-play that uses some linguistic feature which combines two different meanings at the same time. Although puns are usually embedded in words they can also work on other levels of language. Hence, there is variation in their properties. Puns are of the utmost importance in stylistics because they bring together two different elements of language. As Leppihalme (1997) points out, word-play is based on different features of the language(s) involved. For example, pronunciation, morphology, spellings, vocabulary or syntax. Wordplay can be expressed in ambiguous verbal wit, breaking grammar rules and other linguistic forms. The actualization of a word-play or pun is highly dependent on the context which specifies its pragmatic role. The classification of pun put forward by the Chinese scholar Chuandao (2005) is different. He says that the pun is not just connected with the meaning and homophony of a word, but also to the context, manner of speech and logic. He singles out different types of pun; homonymic, lexical, understanding, figurative and logic. While the first two are concerned with sounds, spellings and polysemantic words, the other three highlight the importance of context that determines the meaning of a pun. The understanding pun; which is analyzed in the texts of the study, explains the implied meaning of a sentence through context. Sometimes a sentence does not have a pun-word and it only reveals the implied meaning through a particular context. The figurative pun is the one that has a simile or a metaphor as its surface meaning and the figurative meaning as its deep meaning. Lastly, the logic pun is a rhetorical device, a kind of implication in a context (Giorgadze, 2014).

Puns rarely work in translation due to linguistic differences, but Delabastita (1996) proposes creative strategies like replacing source text pun by a target language pun which may or may not be close to the formal structure, semantic structure or textual function or by some rhetorical device related to the original which aims to recapture the effect of the source text pun. These strategies require more effort and time of the translator but are worthwhile in literary translation. Other than the linguistic differences, cultural differences play an important role in the translation of literary texts. As Sapir-Whorf put it “No two languages are ever sufficiently similar to be considered as representing the same social reality. The worlds in which different societies live are distinct worlds, not merely the same world with different labels attached.” (Sapir, 1929, Considering all the above-mentioned ideas regarding puns and their translation, humorous short stories by Patras Bukhari and their English translations have been selected to analyze the translational loss during the process. It aims to address the loss of actual meaning and essence of the original in the translation of a text. The texts such as the selected short stories, are rich in humor and cultural connotations and display creativity of the author and his command on language. Such texts need to be carefully dealt with during the process of translation, considering also the standing of the author in the literary world and the uniqueness of his expression especially in humor.

ANALYSIS

Pun and its stylistic features:

URDU (ST)	ENGLISH (TT)
شریف	Proper
کلام	Say
زادے صاحب میاں	Dear Boy
گا جائے بخوبی تو بندوبست کا وغیرہ	Other things will take care of themselves
والے چلنے پہ مستقیم صراط	Righteous
ہوں چاہتا ضرور داد سے طبقے کے مردوں	Brotherhood of Men
رہا نہ باقی شک کوئی میں برابری کی دونوں عورت اور مرد	Believed wholeheartedly in the equality of sexes.
بے دوڑتا طرف کی شہر تو ہے آتی موت کی گیٹر	Set my own trap
فریب	Accomplished

At this level, the stylistic features in the ST and TT are discussed. These features include the word-choices, their use in the context that sets the tone of the texts which builds up the stylistic devices and create overall humor in the texts. As discussed in the methodology, different types of puns are analysed. The selected excerpts are the examples of ‘pun’ which is an important and central stylistic device in the humorous texts. It is mainly built on the linguistic ambiguity that is a result of the word-choices in a certain context. The word-choices of the author clearly highlight the idea of a pun that is intended towards the character in the story. However, the word-choices of the translators as explained in this level are not sufficient to set the tone of the ST in the TT or even come close to it in intensity and effect. In the first read of the original the readers are eased into understanding the situation and condition of both the characters. With the use of the words that playfully but by standing strong in the context deliver pun with effect, which is absent in the TT.

On the surface the structural difference of Urdu and English languages is at work, but without any apparent incongruity in the form. It is using different words in the ST and TT that the incongruity becomes apparent and results in the loss of meaning. The author uses more abstract words to create ambiguity and humor. While the translators remain focused on transliterating the words not maintaining their sense and context of use in the TT.

In the TT, the idea of ‘شریف’ with the use of the word ‘proper’ is distorted. The understanding pun that clarifies the intention of the author through the context of its use is distorted. The tone of the author in the ST with the use of the word ‘شریف’ is with the intention to pun Mirza Sahab and his silence. It is to provoke and get a reaction out of Mirza Sahab since in the author’s mind the news that he is going to buy a car is huge enough for his friend to react and feel jealous or at least envious of him. The intensity of the original pun is lost in the TT with the use of ‘proper homes’, because proper has a different use in the English language that hints at the appearance and not on the background and upbringing of an individual. The collective use of ‘proper homes’ means that Mirza Sahab does not belong to a proper home that is well-discipline and organized instead of it implying that Mirza’s silence is not justified and very disappointing for the author. The author’s intention was to impress Mirza Sahab in the context of the story, it is evident from the previous events of the story where the author is annoyed by Mirza Sahab’s constant indifference to his questions and not showing a least bit of interest. The humor lies in the author’s attempt to provoke a response and reaction out of his friend and failing to do so. Similarly, the use of ‘say’, ‘other things’, ‘my dear boy’ and ‘take care’ do not deliver the essence of the ST in the TT. These choices of words overall impact the tone of the excerpt and make it less pleasing or humorous than the ST.

The words in this excerpt, ‘شریف’ and ‘کلام’ when translated as ‘proper’ and ‘say’ disconnect the idea of respect that the author intends to punningly deliver. In the SL culture, ‘شریف’ is used to describe the ‘nobility’ of a person, commenting on how a person belongs to a ‘virtuous’ and ‘noble’ family. This entails that the person must have been brought up well, uses no abusive language, is respectful, disciplined, and follows the rules set by the norms of the society and the religion. To say that ‘بھی الفاظ وہ تمیں’ بولے نہیں میں گھرانے شریف کسی جو ہیں آتے بھئی تمیں’ intends that Mirza knows different languages and words that no ‘noble’ family considers good and his ‘humph’ as an only response to the author’s announcement is a sign of jealousy. Because he could respond to the author’s statements and react to his plans as the author desired and what is considered basic manners and a sign of being ‘شریف’ but instead he is quiet and not saying anything. This puns the fact that Mirza is not ‘noble’, he is a man of knowledge with his ‘speech’ not moving beyond ‘humph’ would only mean that he did not like the idea of the author buying a car. In the TT, ‘you know some words that are never spoken in school, college or in proper homes’ does not portray the same picture or carry the same tone. Because in the TL, proper has a connotation of ‘organised’, ‘well maintained’ and ‘appropriate’ it does not talk about the character of a person, but the way people live. In the context of the story, ‘شریف’ was not meant to reflect on how people live but more like how they are brought up and has some religious element to it as well. Distorting this idea, disconnects the use of ‘کلام’ or ‘say’ as the former, is used with the intention to respect and pun at the same time.

Hence, 'بو جلتے سے مجھ تم' replaced to 'you're jealous of me' loses its impact in the context of use. At the end of the excerpt, the utterance 'میں زبان عربی کو اس بے کیفیت ذہنی تمہاری جو وقت اس' connects all the previous utterances and ideas and the pun is delivered. It is the author's way of hinting that the languages that Mirza knows, one of them (Arabic) has an exact explanation of Mirza's state of mind. The translators, however focus more on the explanation of the word 'حسد' than its use in the context and end up distorting the pun intended. The context of the ST and TT are now in contrast as the intensity of the original is not retained in the TT. By not using the word with similar implications as the ST the context in the TT changes, distorting the element of humor in the original.

Similarly, in the second excerpt, 'زادے صاحب میاں' intends to pun the author on his plans. That his expression of the desire to buy a car must first mean that the author belongs to a 'wealthy family' or is a son of a rich father to have such desires and wishes. This is the tone the author takes and says 'that to buy means to have money and other resources' 'وغیرہ' does not just entail other things it is also a hint at the fact that a lot of planning and preparation is involved in the process of buying a car. The translators continue by saying that 'the other things will take care of themselves', in place of 'گا جائے بخوبی تو بندوبست کا وغیرہ' which is a hint at how the 'et cetera' will be managed to pun the fact that the author ignorantly announced his plan without thinking it through and realizing his lack of resources. In the TT, this utterance described as 'other things will take care of themselves' does not create the same pun as the author intended. The pun that was depended on the ambiguity created in language through the word-choices, hints at the fact that the author requires money and similar resources to buy a car. Secondly, the apparently simple structure of the utterance 'گا جائے بخوبی تو بندوبست کا وغیرہ' also sheds light on the complexity of the task at hand and works as a reality check for the author. The author's wish to impress Mirza by saying that he wants to buy a car falls back at him. And Mirza pointing out that 'وغیرہ' will of course not be arranged either just as the money has not been thought of. The word 'بخوبی' also adds implication that just like the money has not been thought of, the other resources which are not even in consideration will be arranged well, since they are unknown, and it is only the unknown and things which are lesser in value than the money the author can afford. Which is why when 'other things' is used in the context of the story the 'unspecified' element of 'وغیرہ' is lost and the focus shifts to what those other things might be from the importance of money. The tone and the use of these words in the context of the ST collectively bring humor to the situation by creating pun that is only understood in the context which the choices of the translators fail to retain it in the TT. The pun which was directed at the author and his desires appear as simple humorless utterances in the TT. The use of all these words in a certain context reveals the implied meanings of the sentences hence, punning becomes apparent.

Pun and its Context of Use:

There are some religious concepts that cannot be explained through only words, context plays a vital role in the understanding of such concepts. The use of such concepts like 'والے چلنے پہ مستقیم صراط' is an intended pun on the people who are on the right path and follow the rules and directions of the God, even in the modern times and do not approve the author's actions. It is a pun because there hardly is anyone who is not led by his desires and a wish to save face. People who are not involved in bigger crimes or any sins are somehow involved in committing small ones like lying to save their egos and pride. The author intends to pun them and say that only such people who are 'purely on the right path' can disapprove his actions but he needs appreciation from the 'group or stratum' of the men. By this the author also indicates that 'men' would understand his situation because they would have been through the same when dealing with a woman. How they would relate to the author trying to maintain his pride in-front of a woman. This is to hint that men are not 'purely' on the right path and they do stumble just like the author. In our society or the culture of Urdu language in Pakistan, women are looked down upon and men are considered the 'superior' gender. And to maintain their egos men do try to take the path of lying especially when they must defend their intelligence. Although, now its common regardless of the gender still the men are often found lying to save their egos. Which is why the author hints at how his fellow men would understand that how seeing a knowledgeable woman; who knows more than a man is a matter of ego and pride and hence, any kind of face saving becomes necessary and for that adopting all kinds of means is allowed. Also, it is considered that the women are hard to dogde hence, whoever manages to do so deserves to be congratulated. This is how the pun works in this excerpt, 'ہوں چاہتا ضرور داد سے طبقے کے مردوں' translated as 'I want to be congratulated by the brotherhood of men' changes the entire context and the readers of TT would be lost since, the cultural practices are different of the target culture. Even with the idea of 'brotherhood' that shows the author's belonging and brotherhood does not clarify to the readers of the TT as to why are men not among the 'righteous'. Also, in the next excerpt, when the author says 'کی دونوں عورت اور مرد' 'رہا نہ باقی شک کوئی میں برابری' is to refer to the cultural perception of the equality of both genders and how that concept is distorted in the cultural practices of the SL context. Since, this discrimination is not a perceived by-default culture of the TL, it must be carefully presented to the readers of the TT. If the pun is not delivered adequately, the intention gets lost and the humor is not retained which results in its loss. This is the case in the TT, the translators have translated the concept into 'I believed wholeheartedly' it does not portray the same meaning or the intended pun to the readers. The use of 'رہا نہ باقی شک کوئی' hints at the fact that in the SL culture

there are debates going on about the equality of men and women and people still oppress women and think of them as the inferior gender, so when the woman in this story managed to dogde the man he could only accept the fact that men and women are indeed equals. They are equally capable of making fools of each other and win at it. In the context of use it meant to pun the fact that men and women are equal when it comes to fooling each other. The meaning can only be conveyed to the readers of TT, if the word-choices were adequate. The translators could have balanced it out by using 'I became convinced of' to show that he accepted the equality if sexes and how he was convinced of it.

With the use of the words like 'righteous' and 'brotherhood' the tone of the text is changed. What originally was intended as pun only appears to be an average statement made by the translators. The idea of pun lies in the words 'صراط مستقیم پہ چلنے والے' which implies that the people who are pure and do not break any rules and follow the directions of the God cannot approve of the author's actions, but it also hints that there are no completely pious people, who have never done any wrong. The word 'فریب' describes the action of the author was wrong and hence, the words connect ideas of being on a right path and doing the wrong thing which will not be appreciated by the people on the right path but the men.

Also, the use of this with the next choice of 'مردوں کا طبقہ سے داد ضرور چاہتا ہوں' is a pun intended towards the men who are not among the righteous and feel the situation of the author and can understand why he did what he did. However, when this is translated as 'congratulated by the brotherhood of men' it loses the effect and changes the meaning in the TT. Because of the contextual contrast of the TL culture, where the equality of gender is accepted, and men do not portray themselves or think of themselves as the superior gender of the society. Hence, the idea appears to be foreign for the target audience and confuses them.

Similarly, in another excerpt of the same story where the author intends pun on both the genders, male and female to say that they are equally talented in lying and using other incorrect ways to impress others or face saving. The use of 'کوئی شک باقی نہ رہا' and 'believed wholeheartedly' are near in sense but different in meaning. The translators could have used 'no doubts remained in the equality of men and women' to come a little closer to the meaning and build the humorous context as the ST. The pun intended on men and both the genders gets lost in the TT because of the contextual contrast and distortion of meaning.

Pun its Meaning and Implications:

With the use of the metaphor and implied meanings of 'bad luck' and 'misfortune' the tone hints towards the pun intended on the author's condition. That he it was his bad luck that he told or mentioned about his exams to his neighbor. The metaphor and these words are connected in such a way that collectively forms the pun and cannot do without each other. The lack of which distorts the humor and does not create the same pun.

In this excerpt, the metaphor 'بے دوڑتا طرف کی شہر تو بے آتی موت کی گڈر' has been used to point that the author brought whatever happened next on himself. It was the time of his misfortune, or something bad to happen to him that he went to his neighbour. It was his 'misfortune' that took him to Lalaji for help, to ask him to wake him up early in the morning. Lalaji was an early riser himself, which gave the author the idea to seek help from him. The author had been thinking about waking up early in the morning to study and start fresh. To replace these ideas with 'in the end it turned out I had set my own trap' does not really do justice to the expression in the ST. Because it was through this metaphor that the author intended to pun himself and Lalaji. The use of the said metaphor adds the element of humor and gives a different meaning than the TT.

Conclusion

The humor in the selected excerpts from the stories was identified through the words and their effect in the context of use, those words set the tone of the utterances and worked to build up the style of the excerpt. Later, at the stylistic level the devices and techniques were analyzed, based on how they were built in the context of ST and TT. The translational loss is apparent and evident through the analysis conducted on the selected data due to the translators' lexical choices. The humor in the selected excerpts from the stories was identified through the words and their effect on the readers. Those words set the tone of the utterances and worked to build up the style of each excerpt. At this level, the devices and techniques were analyzed, based on how they were built in the context of ST and TT. Each of these devices and techniques through which the humor is built i.e. pun, irony, satire etc. evokes a different kind of effect but altogether of fun, amusement. It became evident, that the translators did not handle the text carefully, their word-choices distorted the context and affected the humorous built-up of the entire text. The utterance that produced a pleasant effect or even laughter in the original had no similar or any effect at all. The words in the translations were simple yet less humorous. The cultural-specific words were distorted in the TT either by creating a completely different picture or by depicting a confusing picture for the readers. It was observed that the translators have focused more on transliteration, related abstract ideas and words with concrete ones in some cases and used words of less intensity. This has resulted in the distortion of the tone of the author, his intention of punning or being ironic in the text and presented the cultural concepts and metaphors and idioms as confused utterances for the readers of the TT. Hence, the context of the

utterances was changed and the deviation in the stylistic devices that was formed resulted in the translational loss of humor.

References

- Abrams, M.H. (1999). *A Glossary of Literary Terms*. Fort Worth: Harcourt Brace College Publishers.
- Baranauskienė, R., & Pociūtė, L. (2012). Challenges of Humour Translation in Fiction. *Jaunųjų mokslininkų darbai*, (3), 48-53.
- Bassnett, S. (2002). *Translation Studies*, Routledge, Traylor and Francis Group, London, New York.
- Broeder, Linda. (2007). *Translating Humour - The Problems of Translating Terry Pratchett*, Igitur Archief - Utrecht Publishing and Archiving Service. Retrieved at June 6, 2012, from the website temoa: Open Educational Resources (OER) Portal at <http://temoa.tec.mx/node/308248>
- Bukhari, P. (2012). *Patras k Mazameen: Kulyat-e-Patras Bukhari*. Lahore: Al-Hamd Publications. (Originally published in 1927)
- Chiaro, D. et al., (2010). *Translation, Humor, and Literature*. Continuum International Publishing group, London, New York.
- Chuandao, Y. (2005). English Pun and its Classification. *Language in India*, Volume 5
- Cisneros, R., et al., (2006). *The Language of Humor: Navajo*, University of New Mexico.
- Delabastita, D. (1996). *Wordplay and Translation*, Special Issue of *The Translator*, Manchester: St. Jerome.
- Giorgadze, M. (2014). Linguistic Features of Pun, its Typology and Classification.
- Gul, T., & Javed, T. (2012). Humour and Satire in Urdu Literature. *Dialogue, Pakistan*, 7(2).
- Guo, H. (2012). A Brief Analysis of Culture and Translation. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, Theory and Practice in Language Studies, Vol. 2, No. 2, February 2012, Academy Publisher, Manufactured in Finland.
- Hossieni, R. B., Mobaraki, M., & Nia, M. R. (2017). A Comparative Study of Transference of Humor in Translations of "The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn" by Mark Twain. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 6(6), 1-8.
- Lei, L. (2010). *Translation of Humor in Ch'ienChungshu's "Weicheng" in Jeanne Kelly and Nathan K. Mao's Version: From the Perspective of Reception Aesthetics*. University of Wisconsin-Platteville. Retrieved September 3th, 2013, from: <http://minds.wisconsin.edu/bitstream/handle/1793/43583/Liu.%20Lei.pdf?sequence=1>
- Leppihalme, R. (1997). *An Empirical Approach to the Translation of Allusions*. Clevedon Multilingual Matters Ltd.
- Munday, J. (2009). *The Routledge Companion to Translation Studies*. Routledge.
- Newmark, P. (1988). *Approaches to Translation*. Hertfordshire: Prentice Hall.
- Raskin, V. (1985). *Semantic Mechanisms of Humor*. Dordrecht, Holland: D. Reidel Pub. Co.
- Rasouli, E., & Rahimi, A. (2015). The Effects of Religion on Translating Humor From English Into Persian Through Figurative Language. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 192, 453-459.
- Reeck, M., & Ahmed, A. (2008). Six Humorous Pieces. *Annual of Urdu Studies*, 23. University of Wisconsin.
- Rumi, R. (2006, August 5). *Patras Bukhari* [web log post]. Retrieved from <https://pakistaniat.com/2006/08/05/guest-post-patras-bokhari/>
- Sapir, E. (1929). The Status of Linguistics as a Science. *Language*, 207-214.
- Simpson, P. (2004). *Stylistics: A Resource Book for Students*. Psychology Press.
- Vandaele, J. (2002). "Introduction – (Re-) Constructing Humor: Meanings and Means", *The Translator*, 8(2), pp. 149-172.
- Venuti, L. (2000). Translation, Community, Utopia. *The Translation Studies Reader*, 485.
- Venuti, L. (2000). "Translation, Community, Utopia", in Venuti, L (ed.) *The Translation Studies Reader*, London: Routledge, 482-502.
- Vermeer, H. (1992). Is Translation a Linguistic or a Cultural Process? *Ilha do Desterro A Journal of English Language, Literatures in English and Cultural Studies*, (28), 037-051.
- Zbaracki, M. D. (2003). *A Descriptive Study of How Humor in Literature Serves to Engage Children in their Reading*, The Ohio State University.

Author Information

Dr. Amna Saeed

Assistant Professor Dept. of Humanities
COMSATS University, Islamabad

Fatima Nagrah

Research Scholar COMSATS University, Islamabad
